

Mo-CeO₂ photocatalysts on MICROSCAFS®: Defect and support engineering for enhanced CO₂ photoconversion

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ABSTRACT

The development of efficient photocatalysts for CO₂ reduction is crucial for the development of carbon-neutral energy systems and sustainable production of fuels. In this study, Mo-modified CeO₂ nanoparticles were synthesized and immobilized on SiO₂-TiO₂ porous microspheres (MICROSCAFS®) to improve charge separation, light harvesting, and surface reactivity. Structural and physico-chemical characterization confirmed the successful incorporation of Mo species into the CeO₂ lattice, leading to enhanced oxygen vacancy formation and improved redox properties. The photocatalysts were evaluated for CO₂ photoreduction, where Mo-CeO₂ demonstrated the highest CO and CH₄ production rates, which can be attributed to modifications in the defect and electronic structure of CeO₂ upon Mo doping, enhancing CO₂ adsorption and activation of CO₂ molecules. The Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® composite further enhanced generation and selectivity towards H₂ owing to its macroporous architecture and higher surface hydroxyl density, which improved water activation. These findings highlight the synergistic interplay of Mo doping and MICROSCAFS® structuring, establishing Mo-CeO₂-based materials as promising candidates for sustainable CO₂ photoconversion into value-added fuels.

1. Introduction

Air pollution and energy crises represent major challenges for modern society [1–3]. The rapid development of industrialization, coupled with exponential population growth, has intensified concerns about environmental deterioration and the sustainability of the energy sector, thereby posing serious risks to both ecosystems and human well-being [4–8]. Data presented by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) underscore the severity of the current situation. According to NASA, the latest measured CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere reached 427.09 ppm (date of measurement: February 15, 2025). This is the highest concentration recorded since 1958 [9].

Fortunately, photocatalysis offers a promising approach to tackling these challenges. Indeed, photocatalytic transformations not only successfully decompose pollutants in water, but also facilitate the conversion of CO₂ molecules into valuable organic compounds such as methane or further processable intermediates like carbon monoxide [1,10–14].

These transformations firmly place photocatalysis among the key strategies for both environmental remediation and waste-to-value conversion [15–17].

Although photocatalysis holds great potential, the efficiency of this pathway remains questionable. Given the current state of photocatalytic technologies, the practical application of this strategy is very limited [18]. Therefore, it is necessary not only to design and assemble new photocatalytic setups, but also to explore and synthesize novel materials to enhance photocatalytic performance, thereby increasing the possibility of implementing this technology in industrial applications.

The choice of material plays a crucial role in photocatalytic processes. The most investigated material in recent years is undoubtedly titanium dioxide (TiO₂), known for its chemical and thermal stability, as well as its low cost. Nevertheless, its wide bandgap (3.2 eV) and the rapid recombination of charge carriers significantly limit its photocatalytic performance [19–22]. Therefore, it is essential to focus the current research on the design and preparation of novel materials, or on

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the development of heterostructured composites based on existing photocatalysts.

CeO₂ has attracted increasing attention as a redox-active photocatalyst due to its Ce⁴⁺/Ce³⁺ cycling and ability to generate oxygen vacancies that promote CO₂ adsorption. Nevertheless, pure CeO₂ suffers from suboptimal charge transport and limited photon harvesting. Elemental doping has been proven effective in stabilizing oxygen vacancy defects and tailoring the electronic structure of CeO₂. In particular, Mo incorporation introduces intermediate energy states and enhances charge separation, which can significantly improve CO₂ conversion efficiency.

In addition to compositional modification, the immobilization of semiconductors on structured supports can enhance practical applicability by preventing nanoparticle agglomeration and facilitating photon accessibility and mass transfer. MICROSCAFS® (porous SiO₂-TiO₂ microspheres) provide a mechanically robust and highly permeable framework that enhances light utilization while maintaining catalyst dispersion [23–25].

Herein, we report the synthesis of Mo-modified CeO₂ nanoparticles immobilized on MICROSCAFS® for enhanced photocatalytic CO₂ reduction. We systematically correlate structure, surface chemistry, electronic properties, and photocatalytic performance to identify key parameters governing product selectivity and efficiency. Our findings highlight the synergistic effect of Mo doping and MICROSCAFS® immobilization as a promising strategy for efficient photocatalytic CO₂ conversion.

In this work, we successfully synthesized CeO₂ nanoparticles (NPs) modified with Mo. To further enhance their photocatalytic efficiency, the prepared Mo-modified CeO₂ NPs were supported on MICROSCAFS® via an ultrasound-assisted process, resulting in a composite material.

The resulting photocatalyst samples were comprehensively characterized using advanced analytical techniques. Subsequently, the photocatalytic performance of the synthesized samples was evaluated in a photocatalytic reaction: CO₂ photoreduction. The photocatalytic activity of the modified samples was compared with that of unmodified CeO₂ NPs and MICROSCAFS®. Finally, the experimental results from the performed photocatalytic tests were correlated with the obtained physicochemical properties of the tested samples. This analysis aimed to clarify the key factors influencing their photocatalytic performance and to better understand their behavior in each reaction.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Cerium (III) nitrate hexahydrate (Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O, 99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich), ethanol (EtOH, ≥99.8% Fisher Chemical), ammonia aqueous solution (NH₄OH, 25%, Chem-Lab), Ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate ((NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O, 99.98%, Merck).

All reagents used in the experiments were of analytical reagent grade and were used without any further treatment or purification, while deionized water was employed throughout the entire experiment for aqueous solution preparation.

2.2. Synthesis of CeO₂ nanoparticles

Cerium dioxide NPs were synthesized by combining a chemical precipitation technique with calcination. First, 16.8 g of Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O was added to pure ethanol and stirred in a beaker for 30 min. After complete dissolution of the Ce-based salt (Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O) in ethanol, the reaction mixture was transferred to a three-neck round-bottom flask and heated up to 70 °C in an oil bath under continuous stirring. Upon reaching 70 °C, 10 ml of NH₄OH was added dropwise to the reaction mixture. This mixture was then stirred for 1 h at 70 °C. Afterwards, the mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature. The resulting precipitate was collected by centrifugation at 4000 rpm and washed with

deionized water and ethanol several times. Finally, the product was dried in a drying oven at 50 °C overnight and further calcined in a muffle furnace at 500 °C with a heating rate of 5 °C/min for 1 h. The final obtained photocatalyst sample was labelled CeO₂.

2.3. Synthesis of Mo-modified CeO₂ nanoparticles

The Mo-modified CeO₂ NPs were synthesized following the same procedure described in Section 2.2, except that a pre-calculated amount of (NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O (to obtain 5 wt% of Mo) was added as the Mo source alongside Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O in the first step of synthesis. The resulting photocatalyst was labelled as Mo-CeO₂.

2.4. Synthesis of Mo-modified CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® composite

The synthesis of the Mo-modified CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® composite can be divided into two parts. First, the porous SiO₂-TiO₂-based microspheres MICROSCAFS® were prepared using an adapted sol-gel technique combined with polymerization-induced phase separation. The detailed procedure for MICROSCAFS® preparation is provided in the Supplementary materials. In the next step, the prepared Mo-modified CeO₂ NPs were immobilized onto the porous MICROSCAFS® via wet impregnation. An ethanolic dispersion of the prepared Mo-CeO₂ NPs was introduced into a container containing the porous MICROSCAFS®. Subsequently, the mixture was sonicated for 5 min and then dried in an oven at 60 °C for 15 h. The final photocatalyst sample was labelled as Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS®.

2.5. Characterization of the investigated photocatalysts

The investigated photocatalysts, listed in Table 1, for better clarity, were comprehensively characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), attenuated total reflectance – Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR), scanning electron microscopy equipped with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), N₂-physisorption, UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-Vis DRS), photoelectrochemical measurements, and Kelvin probe analysis. A detailed description of the performed characterization measurements is available in the Supplementary materials.

2.6. Photocatalytic CO₂ reduction experiments over the investigated photocatalysts

The testing of photocatalytic activity of the investigated samples for CO₂ reduction was carried out in the batch-stirred photocatalytic reactor shown in Figure S1. A detailed description of the performed photocatalytic CO₂ reduction experiments is given in the Supplementary Material.

3. Results and discussion

Comprehensive characterization of photocatalysts represents a crucial step photocatalyst development. Indeed, the outcomes of performed analytical techniques provide detailed insights into their physicochemical properties, which in turn influence their final photocatalytic performance. Based on this fact, the synthesized photocatalysts were subjected to a range of analytical tests to reveal information about these characteristics and thereby understand their behavior in photocatalytic experiments.

3.1. Characterization of the investigated photocatalysts

Since the crystallographic structure of materials can significantly influence their efficiency in photocatalytic reactions, XRD analysis of the investigated photocatalyst samples was conducted. As expected, both the unmodified and Mo-modified CeO₂-based NPs samples exhibited the

Table 1
List of the synthesized photocatalysts.

Sample name
CeO ₂
MICROSCAFS®
Mo-CeO ₂
Mo-CeO ₂ @MICROSCAFS®

presence of characteristic CeO₂ (ICDD PDF–2 No. 01–073–6318). The occurrence of this phase is indicated by reflections from the (111), (200), (220), (311), (222), (400), (331), and (420) planes (Fig. 1a). Furthermore, the obtained results demonstrated the successful immobilization of Mo-CeO₂ NPs on the porous MICROSCAFS®. This is evidenced by the detection of CeO₂ reflections corresponding to the (111), (200), (220), (311), and (222) planes at 2θ values of 28.6°, 33.0°, 47.5°, 56.4°, and 59.1°, in the XRD pattern of Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® sample (Fig. 1b).

The morphology of the synthesized photocatalysts was analyzed using SEM. As shown in Fig. 2a–b, the prepared CeO₂ photocatalyst is composed of irregularly shaped particles and agglomerates of various sizes. Due to clustering, it is very challenging to precisely define particle boundaries and accurately determine their size. Nevertheless, it can be estimated that the particle size lies in the sub-micron range, while the clusters range from sub-micron to micron scale, with some larger

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of the investigated (a) CeO₂-based NPs and (b) MICROSCAFS® composites.

Fig. 2. SEM images of the investigated samples CeO₂ (a–b), MICROSCAFS® (c–d), and Mo-CeO₂ (e–f).

agglomerates reaching up to 20 μm.

In contrast, the MICROSCAFS® photocatalyst exhibits a markedly different morphology. In this sample, the clusters are well-ordered, forming spherical structures approximately several tens of μm in size (Fig. 2c). These spheres consist of densely arranged spherical and semi-spherical particles, each about 1 μm in diameter, forming a porous, interconnected internal structure (Fig. 2d).

Compared to the undoped CeO₂ and MICROSCAFS® samples, Mo doping led to noticeable differences, as depicted in the Fig. 2e–f. The SEM images of Mo-CeO₂ (Fig. 2e–f) reveal densely packed clusters of irregularly shaped particles, which represent the dominant morphology of this sample. This material exhibits a pronounced tendency to form clusters, while the Mo-doping likely contributes to the decrease in the size of the agglomerates. These are smaller, mostly in the range of 1–5 μm, compared to those in the undoped sample CeO₂, which showed denser and larger agglomerates. The individual particle size appears to be in the sub-micron range, approximately below 300 nm, which is well below most of the pores exhibited by MICROSCAFS®.

SEM analysis confirmed the effective immobilization of Mo-CeO₂ NPs on the porous MICROSCAFS® support (Fig. 3). Bright surface features and internal deposits correspond to agglomerates of Mo-CeO₂ NPs. The composite retains the overall spherical morphology of pristine MICROSCAFS®, with minor deviations due to the presence of irregular Mo-CeO₂ clusters. These deposits appear as submicron agglomerates (~100–200 nm) that assemble into secondary aggregates on both the surface and within the pore network, however of smaller dimension as that exhibited by unsupported Mo-CeO₂ NPs, thus preventing

Fig. 3. SEM images of the Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® (a – e), with scale bars of 20, 10, 5, and 2 μm. Cross-section of particles purposely broken before the analysis, revealing the presence of Mo-CeO₂ NPs inside the MICROSCAFS®.

nanoparticle agglomeration. EDS elemental mapping (Figure S2) further confirms that these agglomerates correspond to Mo-CeO₂ nanoparticles distributed throughout the MICROSCAFS® pores and internal surfaces.

To identify the individual functional groups and chemical bonds present, the investigated photocatalyst samples were characterized using the ATR-FTIR analysis. As shown in Table 2 and Fig. 4, both CeO₂ and Mo-CeO₂ samples exhibited broad bands at 3395 and 3397 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 4a and c), corresponding to the O-H stretching vibrations of residual water or surface hydroxyl groups. Both spectra also displayed bands at 1631 and 1633 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 4a and c), indicating the O-H bending vibrations of molecularly adsorbed water [26,27]. Furthermore, the ATR-FTIR analysis revealed weak bands at 1534, 1329, and 1061 cm⁻¹ in the undoped CeO₂ sample (Table 2, Fig. 4a). These modes are attributed to residual nitrate ions (NO₃), likely released from the Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O used as a cerium precursor [28–30]. The measured spectra of these samples (CeO₂ and Mo-CeO₂) also confirmed the presence of

Table 2
The list of the detected functional groups in investigated samples.

Band position (cm ⁻¹)	Characteristic group	Sample
3395 – 3397	O-H stretching mode	CeO ₂ , Mo-CeO ₂
1631 – 1633	O-H bending mode	CeO ₂ , Mo-CeO ₂
1534	NO ₃ ions mode	CeO ₂
1329	NO ₃ ions mode	CeO ₂
1064 – 1065	Si-O-Si	MICROSCAFS®, Mo-CeO ₂ @MICROSCAFS®
1061	NO ₃ ions mode	CeO ₂
955	Mo=O stretching mode	Mo-CeO ₂
931 – 932	Si-OH/Ti-OH	MICROSCAFS®, Mo-CeO ₂ @MICROSCAFS®
840 – 855	Ce-O stretching mode	CeO ₂ , Mo-CeO ₂
795 – 797	Si-O	MICROSCAFS®, Mo-CeO ₂ @MICROSCAFS®
711	Mo-O-Mo mode	Mo-CeO ₂

Ce-O stretching vibrations, which are characteristic of CeO₂-based materials. These correspond to the bands observed at 840 and 855 cm⁻¹ [27,31]. Finally, the spectrum of the Mo-CeO₂ sample confirmed the successful incorporation of Mo species, as evidenced by the detection of Mo=O and Mo-O-Mo modes at 955 and 711 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 4c) [32–35].

In addition to these photocatalysts, the Mo-doped CeO₂ sample (Mo-CeO₂) was also immobilized into the porous MICROSCAFS®, which served as a support, forming the composite photocatalyst – Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS®. However, the ATR-FTIR analysis of this composite (Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS®) revealed only bands characteristic of the porous MICROSCAFS®. Specifically, the obtained spectrum (Fig. 4d) showed bands at approximately 1064, 931, and 796 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the Si-O-Si, Si-OH or Ti-OH, and Si-O, respectively – typical features of the MICROSCAFS® (Table 2, Fig. 4b and d) [24,36,37]. At first glance, the obtained results do not clearly confirm the successful immobilization of the Mo-CeO₂ NPs within MICROSCAFS®. This may be attributed to the low intensity of the FTIR peaks characteristic of Mo-CeO₂ NPs, which may be hidden by the SiO₂ peaks, as well as to the low loading of Mo-CeO₂ NPs in the composite. This interpretation is consistent with the SEM observations, which show no continuous Mo-CeO₂ layer on the MICROSCAFS®, but only discrete NPs clusters sparsely distributed within the pores and on the surface of the support.

On the other hand, the EDS (Figure S2) and XPS results (Figure S3, Fig. 5) indicate the successful preparation of the composite photocatalyst Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS®. This is supported by the semi-quantitative data presented in Table 3, summarizing the elemental analysis of the investigated Mo-doped photocatalysts using SEM-EDS. The analysis revealed the presence of Mo not only in the Mo-CeO₂, but also in the sample after immobilization into MICROSCAFS® – Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® (Table 3).

In addition, the presence of Mo species on the surface of Mo-doped investigated samples (Mo-CeO₂ and Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS®) was confirmed by XPS analysis. This is in line with the observation of Mo 3d_{3/2} and Mo 3d_{5/2} XPS peaks in the Mo 3d XPS spectra, indicating the presence of Mo⁶⁺ species (Fig. 5) [38].

Detailed surface analysis of the samples, performed by XPS, further revealed the presence of lattice oxygen, oxygen vacancies (O_v), and surface O-H groups. These oxygen-based species correspond to the detection of characteristic O 1s peaks at binding energies of ~ 530.1, ~ 531.2, and ~ 532.6 eV. As a result of peak overlap, the precise position of identified peaks maxima may vary by ± 1.2 eV (Figure S4). The quantitative analysis of the high-resolution O 1s XPS spectra also indicates that successful Mo-doping not only increased the formation of oxygen vacancies, which contributes to boosted CO₂ photoreduction activity, but also simultaneously reduced the proportion of surface O-H groups (Table 4).

In addition to Mo- and O-based species, the high-resolution Ce 3d XPS spectra demonstrated the presence of both Ce⁴⁺ and Ce³⁺ species in the CeO₂, Mo-CeO₂, and Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® samples (Fig. 6). The coexistence of these oxidation states is closely linked to electron transfer processes occurring within CeO₂ upon successful Mo-doping. Specifically, when CeO₂ is doped with transition metals such as Mo, the dopant can be incorporated into the CeO₂ lattice, where it can substitute Ce ions and influence the balance between Ce⁴⁺ to Ce³⁺ states. This substitution is also often accompanied by the formation of oxygen vacancies, which can affect the surface reactivity of the sample [39–42].

N₂-physisorption analysis of the investigated photocatalysts revealed that both CeO₂ and Mo-CeO₂ samples exhibit predominantly mesoporous character. This observation corresponds to the presence of type IV adsorption-desorption isotherms according to the IUPAC classification (Fig. 7a) [43]. In contrast, MICROSCAFS®-based samples exhibit a meso-macroporous nature, as evidenced not only by the presence of type IV adsorption-desorption isotherms according to the IUPAC characterization (Fig. 7b) [43], but also by the density functional theory (DFT) analysis, which provides deeper insights into their porosity (Figure S4

Fig. 4. ATR-FTIR spectra of the investigated samples (a) CeO₂, (b) MICROSCAFS[®], (c) Mo-CeO₂, and (d) Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS[®].

Fig. 5. High-resolution Mo 3d XPS spectra of (a) Mo-CeO₂ and (b) Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS[®] samples.

and S5). Additionally, the specific surface area slightly decreased upon Mo-CeO₂ immobilization on MICROSCAFS[®], whereas the amount of adsorbed N₂ is noticeably higher, especially at high relative pressures, for the composite Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS[®] compared to pure MICROSCAFS[®] (Fig. 7b, Table 5). This observation can be attributed to the presence of Mo-CeO₂ NPs agglomerates which provide further mesoporosity to the MICROSCAFS[®] pores walls, which led to the uptake

in N₂ adsorption values at high relative pressures [44–46]. This finding is also consistent with the DFT analysis results, which confirmed a broader and shifted distribution toward larger pores compared to the pure MICROSCAFS[®] sample (Figure S5 and S6) and is in line with observations reported in the state of the art [47].

Optical properties are crucial for evaluating the photocatalytic performance of photocatalysts. To assess these properties, the synthesized

Table 3

Elemental composition of the investigated samples Mo-CeO₂ and Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS®, determined by SEM-EDS.

Sample	Si (wt %)	Ti (wt %)	Ce (wt %)	Mo (wt %)	O (wt %)
Mo-CeO ₂	-	-	76.3	6.3	17.4
Mo-CeO ₂ @MICROSCAFS®	36.0	12.5	10.7	1.4	39.4

Table 4

Quantitative analysis of oxygen species detected on the surface of the investigated photocatalysts, determined by XPS.

Sample	Oxygen lattice (at%)	Oxygen vacancies (at%)	O-H group (at%)
CeO ₂	54.56	1.35	44.09
MICROSCAFS®	3.73	6.39	89.88
Mo-CeO ₂	28.02	33.09	38.90
Mo-CeO ₂ @MICROSCAFS®	6.90	36.40	56.70

photocatalyst samples were analyzed using UV-Vis DRS, and the obtained data were subsequently transformed using the Kubelka-Munk function (Fig. 8).

As shown in Fig. 8, Mo-doped materials (Mo-CeO₂ and Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS®) exhibit a noticeable increase in light absorption in the UV region (200 – 400 nm) compared to their undoped counterparts CeO₂ and MICROSCAFS®. This enhancement is attributed to the successful Mo doping, which improves the light-harvesting ability of the synthesized photocatalyst samples.

In addition, all samples exhibit limited absorption in the visible

range (500–800 nm), as indicated by the low Kubelka-Munk values. Additionally, the absorption edges were further analyzed using Tauc plots to estimate their band gap energies (E_{BG}) and summarized in Table 6. Undoped photocatalysts (CeO₂ and MICROSCAFS®) exhibited higher E_{BG} values than the Mo-doped samples. This decrease in E_{BG} likely results from the introduction of intermediate energy levels associated with the successful incorporation of Mo species, which facilitate the harvesting of photons and thereby enhances photocatalytic efficiency under UV light.

Efficient electron transfer plays a crucial role in photocatalytic processes. To elucidate the dynamics of this step, the transient photocurrent measurements were conducted. The data obtained from these measurements are illustrated in Fig. 9a – d, which depicts the dependence of the generated photocurrent on the applied potential and excitation wavelength. As shown in this figure, two distinct color regions are visible: the blue areas indicate the cathodic photocurrent (corresponding to the reduction of an electron acceptor), while the red areas represent anodic photocurrent (corresponding to the oxidation of an electron donor).

Based on the obtained results (Fig. 9), it is also evident that all investigated samples exhibit very low photocurrent. This behavior is significantly influenced by the presence of pure CeO₂ and SiO₂. Indeed, CeO₂ is well known for its rapid recombination rate of the photo-generated electron-hole pairs, which reflects in a low photocurrent response [48]. In contrast, SiO₂ is characterized by its insulating nature [49]. Thus, the majority presence of SiO₂ in the MICROSCAFS® and Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® samples limits the effective transfer of photo-generated charge carriers, thereby suppressing the photocurrent generation.

Fig. 6. High-resolution Ce 3d XPS spectra of (a) CeO₂, (b) Mo-CeO₂, and (c) Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® samples.

Fig. 7. Adsorption-desorption isotherms of investigated samples: (a) all prepared photocatalysts, (b) magnified region highlighting MICROSCAFS®-based photocatalysts.

Table 5
Specific surface area (S_{BET}) of investigated samples.

Sample	S_{BET} (m ² /g)
CeO ₂	64.8
MICROSCAFS®	5.5
Mo-CeO ₂	44.0
Mo-CeO ₂ @MICROSCAFS®	4.8

Fig. 8. UV/Vis-DRS spectra of the investigated photocatalyst samples.

Table 6
Band gap energies (E_{BG}) of the photocatalyst samples.

Sample	E_{BG} (eV)
CeO ₂	3.10
MICROSCAFS®	3.51
Mo-CeO ₂	2.90
Mo-CeO ₂ @MICROSCAFS®	3.35

3.2. Photocatalytic performance of the investigated photocatalysts for CO₂ reduction

To evaluate the photocatalytic potential of the prepared samples, their performance was first tested in the CO₂ photoreduction process. It should be noted that verification of the carbon source is critical in photocatalytic CO₂ reduction, as carbon-containing products may also originate from residual carbon species or experimental artifacts. In this context, isotope labeling experiments using ¹³CO₂ are widely recognized

as a reliable method to unambiguously confirm the product origin [50]. As shown in Fig. 10, the synthesized Mo-CeO₂-based photocatalysts exhibited significantly enhanced activity for CO₂ photoreduction compared to the unmodified reference samples CeO₂ and MICROSCAFS®. This observation is particularly supported by the yields of the formed CO and CH₄, as described by the following equations (Eqs. 1 and 2) [51,52]:

Mo-CeO₂ exhibited the highest photocatalytic performance for CO₂ photoreduction. This fact is evident not only from the highest yields of carbonaceous products detected after 7 h of CO₂ photoreduction experiments, but also from the highest reaction rate among the tested photocatalyst samples (Fig. 11). In contrast, the reference samples MICROSCAFS® and CeO₂ showed a significant decrease in the yields of carbonaceous products (CO, CH₄), as well as in the calculated reaction rate values. This clearly indicates their poor activity for the performed CO₂ photoreduction tests (Fig. 11).

In addition, since the synthesized samples were tested in an aqueous NaOH solution ($c = 0.2$ M), the influence of the water splitting reaction cannot be neglected. Under these conditions, water acts as the primary electron donor and undergoes oxidation via hole-driven processes, leading to the formation of O₂ as the main oxidation product. This reaction is responsible for H₂ evolution, which was most pronounced for the sample Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® (Fig. 12). However, it is necessary to note that this reaction competes with the CO₂ photoreduction for photogenerated electrons and H⁺ ions, diverting them toward H₂ formation (Eq. 3), rather than toward the generation of CO and CH₄ (Eqs. 1 and 2) [20,53].

Detailed analysis of the obtained results suggests a significant influence of surface oxygen vacancies and hydroxyl groups on CO₂ photoreduction efficiency. Specifically, the correlation shown in Fig. 13a indicates an increasing trend in CO₂ photoreduction performance with the increasing ratio of surface O_v and O-H groups. This effect is likely associated with the presence of the surface oxygen-based species, which promote adsorption of CO₂ molecules and facilitate their following activation [54–58].

In addition, the crucial role of the Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ redox couple should not be overlooked. As depicted in Fig. 13b, the Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ ratio correlates with not only CO₂ photoreduction but also the parallel process of water splitting, as evidenced by the increasing total yields of H₂, CO, and CH₄. The observed correlation suggests that the Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ redox pair, together with defect states introduced through the formation of oxygen

Fig. 9. Photocurrent generation as a function of applied potential and excitation wavelength for (a) CeO₂, (b) MICROSCAFS®, (c) Mo-CeO₂, and (d) Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS®.

Fig. 10. Yields of carbon monoxide and methane after 7 h of the CO₂ photo-reduction process in the presence of the investigated photocatalysts, with error bars indicating a measurement deviation within 5%.

vacancies, may contribute to improved transfer of charge carriers and enhanced photocatalytic performance, which is supported by the electrochemical measurements discussed further in the text (Fig. 1b, Table 7) [59–62].

As previously mentioned, the overall photocatalytic process was influenced by the surface oxygen vacancies, O-H groups, and Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺

Fig. 11. Yields of detected carbonaceous products (CO + CH₄) after 7 h of the photocatalytic CO₂ reduction in the presence of the investigated samples with the calculated values of reaction rate for CO₂ reduction.

redox couple. These factors influenced not only the CO₂ photoreduction but also the simultaneously occurring water splitting reaction. Based on these findings, the selectivity toward H₂ production (as the main product of water splitting) and CO₂ photoreduction were calculated to understand the competitive behavior between these two reactions.

Fig. 12. Yields of hydrogen after 7 h of the CO₂ photoreduction process in the presence of the investigated photocatalysts, with error bars indicating a measurement deviation within 5%.

Calculation was performed using the following equations (Eqs. 4 and 5), where $r(\text{H}_2)$, $r(\text{CH}_4)$ and $r(\text{CO})$ represent formation rates of H₂, CH₄ and CO [63,64]:

$$\text{Selectivity for H}_2 \text{ production} = \frac{[2r(\text{H}_2)]}{[2r(\text{CO}) + 8r(\text{CH}_4) + 2r(\text{H}_2)]} \cdot 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Selectivity for CO}_2 \text{ photoreduction} = \frac{[2r(\text{CO}) + 8r(\text{CH}_4)]}{[2r(\text{CO}) + 8r(\text{CH}_4) + 2r(\text{H}_2)]} \cdot 100\% \quad (5)$$

As shown in Fig. 14, from the CO₂ photoreduction perspective, the Mo-CeO₂ sample exhibits the highest selectivity, promoting the formation of CO. In contrast, the prepared composite Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® shifted the selectivity toward the water splitting, which corresponds to the highest yields of H₂ determined for this sample (Fig. 12). This distinct change in selectivity can be mainly attributed to the higher concentration of surface hydroxyl groups in Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® compared to the Mo-CeO₂ sample. These increase the hydrophilicity of the photocatalyst, which facilitates the adsorption of water molecules. The adsorbed H₂O subsequently dissociates into H⁺ ions (Eq. 6) that interact with photogenerated electrons to form

hydrogen (Eq. 3) [65–67].

In addition to transient photocurrent measurements, cyclic voltammetry was conducted to assess the electrochemical behavior of the investigated samples. As shown in Fig. 15, Mo-doping led to a significant increase in the cathodic current compared to the undoped CeO₂ and MICROSCAFS® samples. This suggests that the Mo-CeO₂ and Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS® samples exhibit more favorable electrochemical behavior for the photocatalytic CO₂ reduction than their undoped counterparts [68]. This observation aligns well with the enhanced photocatalytic activity of the Mo-doped photocatalysts toward the CO₂ photoreduction process, as evidenced by their higher yields of the carbonaceous products compared to the initial samples of CeO₂ and MICROSCAFS® (Fig. 11).

In addition, a detailed analysis of the obtained ΔE_{VB} (energy between the Fermi level and the edge of valence band), work function, and E_{BG} data (Table S1), together with the calculations provided in the Supplementary materials, enables a thorough description of the changes in band alignment and supports the discussion of a plausible defect-assisted photocatalytic mechanism in pristine CeO₂ and its Mo-modified counterpart – Mo-CeO₂. As shown in Fig. 16, it is clear that in pristine CeO₂, the position of the conduction band edge allows, from a thermodynamic perspective, the conversion of CO₂ molecules into the form CO, CH₄, and H₂. In contrast, after Mo doping, the positions of the valence and conduction band edges shift, and the calculated conduction band position of Mo-CeO₂ appears to be thermodynamically unfavorable for a direct conduction band-driven reduction of CO₂ to CO and CH₄ (Fig. 16b). Nevertheless, the Mo-CeO₂ exhibits the highest photocatalytic activity among all tested samples. This apparent discrepancy suggests that enhanced photocatalytic performance cannot be solely explained by the calculated positions of the band edges. Instead, the distinct increase in cathodic current observed for Mo-CeO₂ (Fig. 15) suggests improved interfacial electron transfer and reduction kinetics, which are likely linked to the increased formation of oxygen vacancies,

Table 7
Quantitative analysis of Ce-based species detected on the surface of the investigated photocatalysts, determined by XPS.

Sample	Ce ⁴⁺ (at%)	Ce ³⁺ (at%)
CeO ₂	58.1	41.9
MICROSCAFS®	-	-
Mo-CeO ₂	59.2	40.8
Mo-CeO ₂ @MICROSCAFS®	54.6	45.4

Fig. 13. Correlations between (a) the sum of the yields of carbonaceous products (CO + CH₄) and the surface oxygen vacancies/hydroxyl groups ratio, and (b) the sum of the yields of all detected products (H₂ + CO + CH₄) and the Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ ratio.

Fig. 14. Proportion of CO and CH₄ yields, and calculated selectivity toward H₂ production (as the main product of water splitting) and CO₂ photoreduction obtained from photocatalytic tests conducted in the presence of the investigated photocatalysts.

Fig. 15. Cyclic voltammograms of the investigated photocatalysts.

related defect states, and modifications in the electronic structure induced by Mo incorporation [69–72]. Furthermore, the reduced energy difference between the Fermi level (E_F) and the edge of the conduction band upon Mo-modification of CeO₂ suggests a strengthened n-type character, which may contribute to a higher density of photogenerated electrons participating in surface reduction reactions, such as CO₂ photoreduction [73–75].

4. Conclusions

This research demonstrates that molybdenum-modified CeO₂ is a highly promising photocatalyst for CO₂ photoconversion process due to its enhanced redox properties, abundant oxygen vacancies, and

Fig. 16. Schematic diagrams of the band structures and charge transfer pathways in (a) CeO₂ and (b) Mo-modified CeO₂ (Mo-CeO₂) photocatalysts for photocatalytic CO₂ reduction.

improved light harvesting. Mo doping modifies the defect and electronic structure of CeO₂ and strengthens CO₂ adsorption and activation, resulting in significantly increased CO and CH₄ production compared with pristine CeO₂ and MICROSCAFS®. Moreover, immobilization on porous MICROSCAFS® effectively prevents excessive nanoparticle sintering while enabling the formation of stable submicron-sized Mo-CeO₂ clusters (~ 100–200 nm) distributed across the porous network. This hierarchical arrangement improves mass transport, while the hydrophilic MICROSCAFS® surface favors water dissociation and shifts selectivity toward H₂ evolution. Overall, these findings reveal key structure–property–performance relationships and demonstrate that combining Mo-CeO₂ with MICROSCAFS® allows tuning product distribution between carbonaceous fuels and H₂. The insights gained from this study provide a rational basis for the design and engineering of next-generation photocatalysts and contribute to the development of energy-efficient approaches to CO₂ utilization for sustainable fuel production.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ana C. Marques: Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Marcin Łapinski:** Formal analysis. **Kamila Koć:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Beatriz Trindade Barrocas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Rudolf Ricka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Martin Reli:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Miroslava Filip Edelmánová:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcou.2026.103479](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2026.103479).

Data availability

Data availability: The data supporting the findings of this study will be available after manuscript publication on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17786311>.

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